

EPHX2

(Epoxide Hydrolase 2)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target was identified through a protein quantitative trait locus analysis.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 2.7 (rank #6841, 72.6th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 2.7 out of 5 (rank #6841, 72.6th percentile). The individual score components include 2.7 of 3 for genetics, and 0 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic

and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of EPHX2 is not significantly changed in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. EPHX2 is annotated to GO terms primarily from the Lipid Metabolism and Metal Binding and Homeostasis domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low

confidence measures of expression. The expression of EPHX2 is not confidently detected in any cell types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Epoxide hydrolase 2 (EPHX2) is a selected gene for the development of a target enabling package (TEP) to help drive investigation into EPHX2 function related to Alzheimer’s disease pathology and progression. We have identified and characterized antibodies that bind selectively and reliably to EPHX2, the details of which are discussed below. Further a small molecule inhibitor for EPHX2 is already developed and resides within the AD informer set generated by the University of North Carolina medicinal chemistry group associated with our center (1,2). These resources are freely available to the scientific community with the goal of fostering additional research into the role of EPHX2 in AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Epoxide hydrolase 2 (EPHX2) is a member of the epoxide hydrolase family with dual enzymatic functionality. The C-terminal domain of EPHX2 contains the epoxide hydrolase, which converts epoxides

into dihydrodiols, while the N-terminal domain contains a lipid phosphatase domain that may regulate cholesterol accumulation (3). Genetic variation in EPHX2 is associated with several metabolic and cardiovascular diseases including diabetes (4), stroke (5,6), and hypertension (7). One target of EPHX2 breakdown is epoxyeicosatrienoic acid (EET), a lipid that may play a trophic role in both diabetes associated cardiomyopathy and cognitive dysfunction (7,8). The possible linkage of EPHX2 and cardiovascular pathology may be one point of convergence between EPHX2 and neurodegenerative events in AD, as cardiovascular pathology is linked to increased risk of AD (9). EPHX2 plays a role in the central nervous system too, as it is expressed in both neurons and astrocytes (as noted in the above section), and inhibition of EPHX2 is reported to protect against glutamatergic excitotoxicity by protecting astrocyte survival and subsequent glutamate homeostasis (10). The blood brain barrier (BBB) is the interface of the vascular system and the brain, and is reported to become fenestrated (or leaky) in AD pathology. Inhibition of EPHX2 is reported to decrease BBB dysfunction post-cerebral hemorrhage (11), supporting an ameliorative role of inhibition of EPHX2 in adaptive immune cell entry into the brain. More specifically, several studies have suggested that EPHX2 may play some role in the development of Alzheimer's disease pathology, as inhibition of EPHX2 decreases plaque formation in the brains of AD mice (12). Recently, a large scale brain proteome wide association study identified EPHX2 as differentially abundant in AD brains, but did not appear to be causal for disease (13). Together, EPHX2 is a compelling target for therapeutic investigation in AD, as it may modify several disease state associated traits.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Compound Library

At least one potent, cell active small molecule modulator of this protein is included within the AD Informer Set (1,2). Chemical tools from the AD Informer Set can be used in efforts to validate therapeutic hypotheses related to their protein targets. A physical copy of the AD Informer Set can be ordered via the TREAT-AD website: <https://treatad.org/data-tools/ad-informer-set>.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of EPHX2 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

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